

Tardiness: Students' Cases at Kawit National High School Proposed Interventions

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Abstract:- The research assessed the Cases of Students' Tardiness of the Grade Twelve Students of Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu School Year 2017-2018, as the basis for some proposed interventions. The study employed the descriptive normative survey method utilizing the questionnaire technique resorting to the complete enumeration among the 166 grade twelve students and 20 teachers in the Senior High School Department. It focused on answering questions, on the profile of the grade twelve students, as to the: personal background as regards: age, gender, track enrolled and socio-economic status of parents, educational attainment, combined monthly income of the family and the number of children in the family; the profile of the Senior High School teachers in terms of: personal background as regards: age, gender, civil status, and professional qualification in terms of degree earned, a primary and or minor field of specialization, and length of teaching experience. Based on the indicated findings, it could be briefly stated that there was no significant relationship between age, gender, track enrolled and mostly from other combined monthly family income except P 5, 000.00 – P 9, 999.00 and P 15, 000.00 – P 19, 999.00 and the external and internal factors affecting grade twelve students' tardiness in the Senior High School Department of Kawit National High School; Kawit, Medellin, Cebu for the School Year 2017-2018 hence the computed t-test was higher to 0.05 level of significance which denoted a very high correlation leading to the acceptance of null hypothesis as shown on Table 10. With the indicated conclusion, most notably in the cases of students' tardiness, and external and internal factors, it was therefore recommended that the herein formulated interventions for a development program be strictly implemented.

Keywords: External Factors, Internal Factors, Interventions, Tardiness.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ The Rationale of the Study

Since life is immemorial and practical, man will achieve his goal toward his virtues in the different aspects of human behaviour and living. A *virtue* is a trait deemed to be

spiritually, physically and morally sound, which generally results in the gaining or maintaining of your values. Virtues are the essence of the character. If we keep the virtues at the heart of everyday life, we live with beauty and purpose. One the examples of good virtues to achieve a desired goal is punctuality. Punctuality or being early is commonly characterized as persistence or consistency in working on time (Connors, 2012). It is also an attitude of completing a required task or accomplishing an obligation on or before the designated schedule. Punctuality is one of the rectitudes beyond reproach. Much of the time, effort, energy and wealth will be saved if this virtue is carried out to the whole system of every responsible citizen.

Punctuality will cover all of the positive actions in all aspects of life. Though it was less appreciated by people in other situations like productivity against punctuality, nonetheless, it is still essential in situations that needed it the most. In educational practice, punctuality is an essential trait or quality of the teacher. It is a substratum. Not an embellishment (Boyd K. Packer, 1924-2015). It is about something other than being on time. It is about respecting our devotions. Educators should emphasize the importance of class attendance in school. School can become or be considered as a temple of learning only when the student, the parent or guardian and the society, in harmony, endeavour to make it a place of pursuit for education, a *sadhana*, where the spring of sanctity and thirst for knowledge flows (Narendra Modi, 1950-present). Moreover, an educational institution makes students competent and skilful individuals by attending classes regularly and on time, learning and practising by heart what is being taught relevant to acquiring knowledge and skills through the good values and attitudes they learn along the way.

Nowadays, students' tardiness has been a problem for years. Consistently and often tardy in the flag ceremony, attending classes after recess in the morning and afternoon class sessions and even the first period in the afternoon session. There are instances when transferring rooms to their specialization subjects in Technology and Livelihood Education and other activities like Physical Education subjects; they are late in attending the prescribed schedule. When students reach school or class late, it can abruptly disrupt the flow of the discussion, distract other students,

impede learning, and generally diminish class morale. Moreover, lateness can become chronic and spread throughout the entire class if left unchecked. There are several reasons students arrive to class late; considering the root cause of the problem can help guide instructors to appropriately give responses and strategies. Understanding the reasons, however, does not require condoning the behaviour (www.cmu.edu/teaching/solveproblem/strat-latetoclass/). Unsurprisingly, students with high tardiness rates earn lower grades, and the worst is they cannot cover up the essential lessons as discussed by their teacher. Teachers find it very inconvenient as the momentum of the class only remains smooth and coherent if one of the students enters late.

Furthermore, it also interrupts teachers' average pace and hinders the flow of the time management plan of the teachers. The problem, as mentioned earlier, remains significant in both rural and urban schools. Thus, it is a long line of thought that the researcher picked up this problem to determine factors affecting Senior High School students'

tardiness, precisely Grade Twelve students in Kawit National High School Kawit, Medellin, Cebu School Year 2017 - 2018, and to identify interventions to promote a hundred per cent attendance of the class.

➤ *Theoretical Background*

The Study focused on the idea that one hundred per cent class attendance tends to lead toward a commendable performance of the students in the schools.

➤ *Legal basis of Philippine Education*

As stated in the 1987 Philippine Constitution Article XIV of Section 1, the State shall promote the right of every citizen to access quality education at all levels and use appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all. The provision spells out the right of every Filipino to be given a high-quality education. It has free and compulsory access to education no matter what gender he/she is, able or disabled, to fill up their empty minds and to be the agents of change to promote building the nation.

Fig 1 The Theoretical Framework

➤ *Theories on Quality Education*

As correlated in an education theory offering quality education to young minds, instructional theory explicitly guides how to help people learn and develop effectively. This focused on how to structure and build material for cultivating and promoting the education of human beings, particularly the youth since they were the hope of the fatherland. Moreover, students must go to school regularly and on time to gain experiences, ideas, information and relevant prior knowledge to acquire better learning and to perform various cognitive tasks in school as one of the products of quality graduates.

➤ *The Thrust toward Quality Education*

The standard for global competencies, as of today, is ‘Quality Education’. Catering quality education among students is the most significant responsibility of all concerned individuals, especially classroom teachers. The country's future depends on quality graduate education, from teachers to young ones. It provides all learners the capabilities they require to become economically productive, contributes to peaceful and democratic societies, and develops a strong foundation for continued education essential to personal and professional fulfilment (<https://www.wob.be/en/education/our-vision-on-quality-education>). With quality education, competent and highly skilled graduates can be produced.

Nelson Mandela (1918-2013), in his notable quote about education that ‘Education being the most powerful tool or weapon which you can use to change the world’, is a continuous process that opts to promote holistic and quality education to hone competitive graduates as this will be the key to transform lives of the many.

➤ *The Teacher and the Quality of Teaching*

According to Avul Pakir Jainulabdeen Abdul Kalam, better known as A. P. J. Abdul Kalam (1931-2015), India's 11th President from 2002 to 2007, "Teaching is a very noble vocation that shapes the good moral character or values, calibre, and future of an individual." It is the process of giving knowledge to students. The teacher serves as the heart of the school and is the determinant in a classroom situation. The teacher greatly influences the students who come to school throughout the year. A good and excellent teacher enhances the mind, transforms lives and touches the heart. A teacher has two essential traits that must be possessed; professional and personal qualities. Professional qualities are mastery of the subject matter, understanding of the learner, the teaching principles and other branches of knowledge in the teaching profession. Personal qualities include how teachers relate to students' nature and background in their personalities, interests, attitudes, beliefs and working relationships with students. In short, a teacher dramatically affects students' attendance in day-to-day teaching encounters.

Good teaching emanates from an outstanding teacher, whose consequences are good student performance and perfect class attendance. Effective teachers are essential in student achievement and performance

(<https://www.ernweb.com/educational-research-articles>).

Since there is an effective and efficient teacher in the classroom, students can consistently achieve well. Teachers can also affect how the student patiently and passionately attends their classes. It is their strategy how to handle varied learners to promote a hundred per cent attendance.

➤ *The Quest for a Hundred per Cent Attendance*

Teachers play a vital role in determining student tardiness. The question is, how will teachers reduce student tardiness? Studies show four essential steps to reduce student tardiness in classes: motivate the students, identify the causes, step-by-step help, and expect incremental change.

➤ *Motivate the Students*

Motivation is usually essential in stopping lateness because so many students see no reason to be on time. Convincing students that on-time behaviour is an important skill often generates more change than any other approach.

➤ *Identify the Causes*

Students have problems with punctuality for many reasons, including distractions, cultural differences, skill deficiencies and poor motivation. To most effectively build on-time behaviour, identify and address the source or the leading causes of their chronic lateness.

➤ *Step-By-Step Help*

Once the source of the lateness has been identified, offer step-by-step help. Teachers must extend their time in addressing the said issue to delineate tardiness.

➤ *Expect Incremental Change*

Students whose tardiness is primarily due to skill deficiencies or cultural or background differences may show slow learning and improvement. Mastering new skills requires ample time and constant practice to hold reasonable expectations. Students often detect and react negatively to adults' impatience. The pace of change may be faster in students whose tardiness is primarily due to motivational problems. When finally and properly convinced that punctuality is essential, these students can change their behaviour rapidly (<https://www.youthchg.com/tardiness/>).

➤ *The Proposed Interventions For Students' Tardiness*

Teachers are the agents of change. They are said to be the transformer of the nation's young minds. Teachers are the students' second parents that greatly influence students' behaviour toward the class. Since tardiness is one of the main problems in the working institution of the researcher, interventions can significantly help eliminate students' chronic lateness.

Interventions, as defined in the dictionary, are the act of interposing one thing or something between or among others to make things better (<https://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary/intervention>).

These are a set of possible solutions to address the main issue.

All the cited facts point out that student tardiness really is a never-ending quest among teachers in the academe, whatever sector there is- teaching or non-teaching – or whatever. As such, there is really a need among teachers to look into the student's tardiness to maintain quality education and to meet the ever-growing demands of society. Students who have no late tend to perform in class to their optimum level.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

➤ *Related Literature*

The schools, both private and public, in every country share the significant dilemma of struggling with the attendance duo of absenteeism and tardiness. For this Study, student tardiness was the main point. Lateness or tardiness is the most recurring and "serious problem" schools are having with their students or pupils nowadays (Sprick & Daniels, 2007). In Georgia Secondary Schools, Moore (2010), in his Study on the best practices employed by Georgia Secondary School administrators, that student tardiness is one of the most continuing problems and one of the top five most rampant problems in 21st century high schools. One factor that stresses a student's performance is his/her punctuality, getting to school on time or being tardy or late. Students are often tardy for a variety of reasons. Significant causes of tardiness were categorized as student issues, school factors and personnel factors, such as teacher inconsistency and lack of administrative and teacher presence within the four walls of the classroom. However, if being chronically late to class becomes a habit, it will negatively affect their performance and success in school. According to Dennis Carcomo (2014), in philstar.com issue dated September 26, Private High Schools in Manila proposed to start classes after 8 AM under the proposal of FAPSA President Eleazardo Kasilag to improve and trace the attendance of the students to decrease tardiness and to increase the academic performance of students on core subjects like English, Math, Science, Social Studies and etc.

On the other hand, in the community with small businesses, many managers or department heads struggle with the tardiness of employees in the workplace. The value of punctuality was abolished. It is a significant dilemma that companies face right now, for it will not progress in their firm, department, or organization. As a result, tardiness will often rob opportunity to co-employees and will dispatch forces of workers, as Niccolo Machiavelli (1469-1527), an Italian Politician, had said.

Arreglo (2017), the SSG moderator of Kawit National High School, Kawit Medellin, Cebu, as interviewed by the researcher, stressed that Grade 12 students under Senior High Department are the ones who are chronically tardy, especially in the flag ceremonies and in attending the first subject in the morning session. Moreover, the researcher focused on this problem in his working station to address the main issue and to find out possible interventions to eliminate

the said problem. That is why schools nowadays often establish an attendance policy that includes punishment for multiple tardinesses. Implementing firm policies will help schools promote and encourage students' traits such as accountability and punctuality that they can carry even after they finish school or at their adulting stage.

➤ *Related Studies*

Students' tardiness behaviour is considered a pandemic disease that spreads and infects other students, which leads them behind the discussion and becomes chronic among students. When students come to class late or tardy, they miss the vital information as per injected to their teachers, and they distract other classmates and schoolmates from missing it too. Moreover, it can disrupt the flow or rhythm of the teacher's lecture, and valuable learning time is lost. Nakpodia and Dafiaghor (2011) stressed that tardiness not only means the problem of the late student, but it affects the surrounding people as a whole. Santillano (2010), in her Study, said that psychological theorists considered some "personality traits, including low self-esteem and anxiety" as significant factors of tardiness.

However, some theorists consider that tardiness is an "innate quality" since our being early or late is "considered as biologically determined"; other experts believe that some are "chronically tardy" and hence, that they consciously and unconsciously acquire good things from it. Since tardiness is a never-ending quest among teachers in schools, both public and private, around the globe, interventions are generally the answer to combat the said issue. Some educational institutions implemented student attendance policies as a role of schools' commitment to providing a supportive learning environment that authorizes all students selected to study with the school to fulfil their absolute potential. In addition, teachers should make sure that policy and consequences for lateness have exceptions and seek feedback or pre-conference from students before they act to handle students' lateness behaviour.

ETC (2009) reported that the attendance and punctuality policy clearly implies that regular and punctual attendance is central to ensuring that all students have full quality access to the curriculum and the school. Moreover, tardiness is what Johnson (2011) calls an issue for "which there are no common or easy answers" (p. 78). Thus, late negatively affects the individual student's academic achievement; students or pupils that are punctual and with better attendance has higher grades, while students with poor attendance and always being late have lower grade point averages, respectively.

➤ *The Problem*

The research ascertained the cases of students' tardiness at Kawit National High School: Kawit, Medellin, Cebu, precisely grade twelve students, during the school year 2017-2018 as the basis for some proposed interventions.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

To have a clearer insight into the subject under Study, the following inquiries were formulated.

- *What is the grade twelve students' profile, as to their:*
 - ✓ *Personal Background, as Regards:*
 - *Age;*
 - *Gender;*
 - *Track Enrolled; and*
 - *Socio-Economic Status of Parents?*
- *What is the profile of the senior high school teachers in terms of:*
 - ✓ *Personal Background, as Regards:*
 - *Age;*
 - *Gender; and*
 - *Civil Status?*
 - ✓ *Professional Qualification, as Regards:*
 - *Degree Earned;*
 - *Major/Minor Field of Specialization; and*
 - *Length of Teaching Experience?*
- *What are the factors affecting Grade Twelve Students' Tardiness in terms of:*
 - ✓ *External Factors, as Regards:*
 - *Distance of Home From School;*
 - *Mode of Transportation;*
 - *Time of Travel;*
 - *Time to Transfer from one Room to another; and*
 - *Subjects Disliked and Reasons for Disliking Such.*
 - ✓ *Internal Factors, as Regards:*
 - *How Parents Value their Education;*
 - *Reasons why you are Late in Attending Classes;*
 - *Time Management;*
 - *Learned from the Subject for almost Ten Months;*
 - *Time To Sleep; and*
 - *A Description of the Subject Teacher.*
- *Is there a significant and vital relationship between gender, track enrolled, combined family income and the factors affecting the tardiness of the grade twelve students?*
- *Is there a significant and vital relationship between the external factors and the internal factors affecting grade twelve students' tardiness?*
- *Based on the findings, what are some interventions that can be proposed to eliminate student tardiness of the grade twelve students in Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu?*

➤ *Statement of Hypothesis*

Based on the problem, the following hypotheses were formulated:

- *Ho: No significant relationship between the gender, track enrolled, combined monthly family income and the factors affecting the tardiness of the Grade Twelve Senior High School students.*
- *Ha: A significant relationship between the gender, track enrolled, combined monthly family income and the factors affecting tardiness of the Grade Twelve Senior High School students.*
- *Ho: No significant relationship between the external and internal factors affecting the tardiness of Grade Twelve Senior High School students.*
- *Ha: A significant relationship between the external and internal factors affecting the tardiness of Grade Twelve Senior High School students.*

➤ *Significance of the Study*

The Study's findings could be beneficial to the following individuals who are concerned with students' tardiness as indicated hereunder.

• *Administrators*

The findings of this Study might enable the administrators to do something to improve the competency of the teachers handling the said issue. School heads could motivate the teachers to apply new strategies and innovative techniques in instruction by providing administrative support and by letting them attend training and seminars vital to an effective teaching-learning process to eliminate students' tardiness.

• *Teachers*

Based on the findings of the Study, teachers need to do some interventions so as to motivate and encourage students to strive in their studies for excellence. They might try out some innovative measures to eliminate the students' tardiness to improve the quality of education.

• *Parents*

As one of the benefactors of this Study, parents could give moral support and explain the value of education in real life, for it was the only way to find decent jobs in the different fields of endeavour receiving such benefits.

• *Students*

The students were the direct beneficiaries of this Study. With the proper guidance, enlightenment and encouragement of the teachers, the students could be oriented on the importance of attendance based on the findings in the Study and be motivated and guided to strive more for the better to become creative, morally upright, productive, competitive and skilled individuals to meet the ever-growing demands of the society.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This was quantitative research utilizing the descriptive-normative survey method using a modified questionnaire on tardiness. This primarily sought to find out the prevalent factors affecting Grade Twelve students' tardiness in Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu School Year 2017 - 2018.

The Study centred on the tardiness of grade twelve students in Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu School Year 2017 - 2018. The researcher used the descriptive-questionnaire technique in the gathering of data. The gathered data were then treated using the simple percentage formula, Weighted Mean, Coefficient of contingency, Pearson r and T-test. The outcomes of the Study were used as the basis for providing some proposed interventions to eliminate tardiness at the High School.

➤ *The Flow of the Study*

Fig 2 The Flow of the Study

➤ *Environment*

The research was conducted in Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu.

The High School is situated in the northern part of the province known as the Sugar Bowl of Northern Cebu, which is Medellin. It is mainly found along the provincial road, 132 kilometres from Cebu City. It is accessible by a three-hour drive by a private vehicle or a three and half hour drive by a Ceres Liner from the Cebu City North Bus Terminal. Figures 3 and 4 are maps that show the location of the High School.

As an educational institution, the High School was founded on the year 1975 with the late Mrs. Gloria M. Tajo as the School Principal and formerly known as Kawit Barangay High School. It started with more than 50 students in the first year and was housed in the extra classrooms of the elementary. By the year 1978-1979, a complete four-year secondary course was offered to the barangay folks of Kawit, the recipients of which were those who belonged to the marginal.

Fig 3 Map of Medellin Showing the Location of the Research Study

Fig 4 Map of Cebu Province Showing the Location of the Research Locale

Families Honourable Petronilo Villarín, a former S.B. Member from Barangay Kawit, authored a resolution asking the Municipality of Medellin to donate a parcel of the land area of 8 896. 55 sq. m. located at Sitio A.E. Lunas to separate the elementary and secondary schools. Finally, it was donated to the Department of Education, Division of Cebu Province. The school site is now 1.50 km away from Barangay Kawit Proper and 7 km. away from the Poblacion of Medellin.

With the sudden increase in the population of the school, several classrooms were constructed, and makeshift rooms were made. To date, the school is called Kawit National High School and is named and considered to be the

mother school in the Municipality of Medellin. Since then, it has sought to cater quality and excellent education and relevant services to all the people in the community.

➤ *Methods and Procedures*

The Study employed universal sampling or complete enumeration among the one hundred sixty-six (166) grade twelve students in the senior high school.

➤ *Instrument*

The Study used the descriptive-normative survey questionnaire. The modified questionnaire on the personal profile of the students and teachers, the socio-economic status of parents and the factors affecting the tardiness was

fielded among the Grade Twelve students as the primary respondents of the Study.

➤ *Respondents*

The Study's respondents were the Grade Twelve students of the High School, specifically in the Senior High School Department. There were 166 students enrolled in the different tracks of K to 12 programs, such as General

Academic Strand (GAS), Carpentry, Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM), Information and Communications and Technology (ICT) and Food and Beverages Services (FBS) during the entire school year 2017 - 2018.

Table 1 shows the research respondents by curricular programs/track enrolled.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents by Curricular Program or Track Enrolled

Curricular Program/Track Enrolled	Total Number of Respondents	Percentage
XII-GAS	25	15.06
XII-CARPENTRY	33	19.88
XII-EIM	23	13.86
XII-FBS	64	38.55
XII-ICT	21	12.65
Total	166	100.00

➤ *Data Gathering*

The researcher prepared a letter request asking permission from the School Principal of the High School to have access to students' personal profiles.

The data gathering process was done through the descriptive-normative approach by obtaining the age, gender, track enrolled, teachers' personal profile, socio-economic status of parents and most of all, the factors affecting grade twelve students' tardiness school year 2017 - 2018.

As soon as the needed data were available, treatment of the same immediately followed.

➤ *Category of the Factors Affecting Tardiness*

The data gathered were tallied and scrutinized accordingly. The complexity of the questionnaire was intentionally prepared to extract valid and trustworthy answers from the subject population. The explicit outcomes of the answers were categorized into factors that affect their punctuality values in attending their classes or their learning-related activities.

These will be classified as **External** and **Internal Factors** and further classified according to the details of each factor. The elucidations of the findings were presented in statistical and technical languages, which will generally benefit the readers as well as the subjects of the Study. Thus, the presentations were done according to the researcher's intention to shed light on this tricky rationalization.

➤ *Scoring*

The following scales were used in the scoring of data gathered pertaining to external and internal factors affecting students' tardiness.

• *External Factors*

To give due consideration to other factors that affect the tardiness of the students, the researcher made a survey on the following external considerations, which comprises numbers 1-8 of the survey questionnaire: distance of home from school, mode of transportation, time of travel, time to transfer from one room to another and subjects disliked and reasons for disliking.

Table 2 Scoring on the External Factors Affecting Student's Tardiness

Weight	Category/Scale	Verbal Description
5	Very Much Affecting (VMA) 4.21 – 5.00	The external factors are very much affecting students' tardiness.
4	Moderately affecting (MA) 3.41 – 4.20	The external factors are moderately affecting students' tardiness.
3	Affecting (A) 2.61 – 3.40	The external factors are affecting students' tardiness.
2	Less Affecting (LA) 1.81 – 2.60	The external factors are less affecting students' tardiness.
1	Not Affecting (NA) 1.00 – 1.80	The external factors are not affecting students' tardiness.

• *Internal Factors*

This information gives us the details on how they spend their residual time after classes or while class is going on. This comprises numbers 9-16 of the questionnaire. These factors are time management, the subject/s they don't like most, reasons for disliking the subject, how their time is spent after school, personal reasons why they are late in attending classes, personal view on their degree of learning, personal view about their teachers and their time in going to bed to sleep.

Table 3 Scoring on the Internal Factors Affecting Student Tardiness

Weight	Category/Scale	Verbal Description
5	Very Much Affecting (VMA) 4.21 – 5.00	The internal factors are very much affecting students' tardiness.
4	Moderately affecting (MA) 3.41 – 4.20	The internal factors are moderately affecting students' tardiness.
3	Affecting (A) 2.61 - 3.40	The internal factors are affecting students' tardiness.
2	Less Affecting (LA) 1.81 – 2. 60	The internal factors are less affecting students' tardiness.
1	Not Affecting (NA) 1.00 – 1.80	The internal factors are not affecting students' tardiness.

➤ Treatment of Data

The data gathered in the Study were quantified and treated using the following computation.

- *Percentage*

To find out the distribution of respondents in every curriculum program or track enrolled, the percentage was used.

- *Weighted Mean*

The weighted mean was used to assess the extent of age, gender, track enrolled, socio-economic status of parents and the factors affecting students' tardiness.

- *Coefficient of Contingency*

The coefficient of contingency (c) was used to prove the correlation between the age, gender, track enrolled and the internal and external factors affecting the tardiness of the Senior High School students.

- *Pearson R*

The Pearson r was used to determine positive, negative and linear relationships between variables.

- *T-test*

The T-test validated the degree of significance of the correlation value.

➤ Definition of Terms

Some terms were hereunder identified as utilized in this Study and should be understood to mean as accordingly indicated unless otherwise specified, as the case might be.

- *Administrative Support*

It is the aid from the school head toward the teacher and the students in addressing the main issue to resolve by giving some interventions.

- *Category of the Factors Affecting Tardiness*

The Internal and External Factors and further be classified according to the details of each factor.

- *Educational Attainment*

It pertains to the level of education finished by the student's parents as one subject of the Study. This expressed a post-graduate, college graduate and elementary school level, high school level and elementary and high school graduate, who were the bases for one's occupation or work.

- *External Factors*

The external considerations like distance of home from school, mode of transportation, time of travel, time to

transfer from one room to another, subject/s they don't like most and reasons for disliking the subject.

- *Factors Affecting Students' Tardiness*

The dimensions which have a bearing on the school in one way or another have influenced the students' attendance of Grade Twelve Students.

- *Internal Factors*

The detail on how they spend their residual time after classes or while class was going on.

- *Interventions*

The possible solutions that were set to eliminate the said issue in the school.

- *Occupation*

The livelihood activities engaged in by a person in order to earn money or were the basis for one's educational attainment, and most often, a person who has high educational attainment will have a high-paying occupation.

- *Personal Background*

The personal information of the respondents is the subject under Study.

- *Size of the Family*

The number of dependents or the number of persons living in one household who were supported by the income of the family. As such, it included the legitimate children, aunts, uncles, grandparents or other relatives who were not engaged in livelihood activities.

- *Senior High School*

The term covered the last two years of the K to 12 curriculum and included Grades 11 and 12.

- *Socio-Economic Status*

It was the level indicative of both the economic position and social position of an individual or a group.

- *Tardiness*

The quality of being late, behind time or not on time significantly affected the performance of the students in school.

- *Track Enrolled*

The field of specialization they enrolled in was Senior High School.

IV. SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The chapter treated the summary of the Study, most notably the findings, the conclusions and the recommendations.

A. Summary

The Study ascertained the cases of students' tardiness at Kawit National High School: Kawit, Medellin, Cebu, precisely Grade Twelve students, during the school year 2017-2018 as the basis for some proposed interventions.

The Study focused on answering some specific questions, as follows;

- *What is the grade twelve students' profile; to their:*
 - ✓ *Personal Background, as Regards:*
 - *Age;*
 - *Gender;*
 - *Track Enrolled; and*
 - *Socio-Economic Status of Parents?*
- *What is the profile of the senior high school teachers in terms of:*
 - ✓ *Personal Background, as Regards:*
 - *Age;*
 - *Gender; and*
 - *Civil Status?*
 - ✓ *2.2 Professional Qualification, as Regards:*
 - *Degree Earned;*
 - *Major/Minor Field of Specialization; and*
 - *Length of Teaching Experience?*
- *What are the factors affecting Grade Twelve Students' Tardiness in terms of:*
 - ✓ *External Factors, as Regards:*
 - *Distance of Home from School;*
 - *Mode of Transportation;*
 - *Time of Travel; and*
 - *Time to Transfer from one Room to another; and*
 - *Subjects Disliked and Reasons for Disliking Such.*
 - ✓ *Internal Factors, as Regards:*
 - *How Parents Value their Education;*
 - *Reasons why you are Late in Attending Classes;*
 - *Time Management;*
 - *Learned from the Subject for almost Ten Months;*
 - *Time to Sleep; and*
 - *A Description of the Subject Teacher.*
- Is there a significant and vital relationship between gender, track enrolled, combined family income and the factors affecting the tardiness of the grade twelve students?

- Is there a significant and vital relationship between the external factors and the internal factors affecting grade twelve students' tardiness?
- Based on the findings, what are some interventions that can be proposed to eliminate student tardiness of the grade twelve students in Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu?

The descriptive-normative survey method was utilized during the survey and the analysis of data in a complete enumeration or universal sampling method of 5 identified tracks with six sections in the Senior High School Department of Kawit National High School having 166 students officially enrolled and 20 Senior High School teachers of which data was subjected to the percentage and the average weighted mean. This primarily sought to find out the prevalent factors affecting Grade Twelve students' tardiness in Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu, School Year 2017 - 2018.

B. Findings

➤ *Profile of the Respondents*

The Grade Twelve Students and the Senior High School Teachers.

• *Students*

As a whole, the profile of the students could be summarized in two sub-aspects, the personal and the socio-economic status of the parents.

Pertaining to personal background, the appropriate school level **age** of Grade Twelve students was 18 - 19 with 106 or 64 per cent and was predominantly female with 85 or 51 per cent. As to **gender**, and mostly in the scenario of the Philippine classroom setting, the majority of the class were from Food and Beverage Services (FBS), with 64 or 38.55 per cent as **track enrolled**. The socio-economic status of parents of the respondents could be surmised that they belonged to the DDU sector (depressed, deprived and underserved) considering that the parents with regard to their educational attainment—**fathers**, with 45 or 27.11 per cent were elementary level and 26 or 15.66 per cent having attained the diploma in the elementary and **mothers**, 68 or 40.96 per cent was elementary level and 18 or 10.84 per cent graduated elementary; having a combined monthly family income of P 4,999.00 and below with 47 or 28.31 per cent; and with prominent families mostly with father and mother as parents of four to six children or siblings living in one household with 81 or 48.80 per cent whose fathers' occupation was majority labourers with 64 or 38.55 per cent and whose mothers' occupation also was plain housewives with 146 or 87.95 per cent.

• *Teachers*

The profile of the Senior High School teachers was categorized into two sub-aspects, namely: personal and professional qualifications.

For the personal background of the teacher respondents, this could be succinctly stated as below **age** 35 for a majority 26-35, with 9 or 45 per cent and 25 and below, with 5 or 25 per cent, typically female as to **gender** with 13 or 65 per cent, primarily single with 11 or 55 per cent; married with 8 or 40 per cent and annulled with 1 or 5 per cent respectively.

The professional qualification of the Senior High School teachers could be summarily pointed out almost entirely as bachelor's degree with master's units with 18 or 90 per cent; 1 or 5 per cent having master's degree with doctorate units and bachelor's degree alone as to the **degree earned**. As to their **major /minor field of specialization**, Mathematics and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) were the usual major of concentration of the teachers in teaching grade twelve students with 6 or 30 per cent, followed by English with 5 or 25 per cent; Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) with 2 or 10 per cent and Values Education with 1 or 5 per cent. As to the **length of teaching experience**, they had rendered service mostly ranging from 2 to 5 years with 8 or 40 per cent; 1 year and below with 7 or 35 per cent; 21 and above with 3 or 15 per cent and 11 to 15 years with 2 or 10 per cent.

➤ *External and Internal Factors Affecting Grade Twelve Students' Tardiness*

• *External Factors*

Basically, as to this factor, grade twelve students live about 500-999 meters away from school with 73 or 43.98 per cent, will usually ride a tricycle or the so-called "chappy" with 105 or 63.25 per cent and will travel at approximately 10 minutes with 77 or 46.39 per cent. In addition, the majority of them responded, 121 or 72.89 per cent, that they would be late in attending the next class for they would transfer to their classroom at approximately 5 minutes.

• *Subjects Disliked and the Reasons for Disliking the Subject*

Generally, as to subjects disliked, it could be deduced that Mathematics was majority the subject they didn't like most, with 88 or 35.77 per cent; English with 57 or 23.17 per cent; Science by 44 or 17.89 per cent; Araling Panlipunan by 27 or 10.98; Filipino by 16 or 6.50 per cent; Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health (MAPEH) by 9 or 3.66 and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) by 5 or 2.03 per cent respectively.

As to **reasons for disliking such a subject**, it could be inferred that they don't like the subject itself 112 or 67.47 per cent; they also don't like the teacher 41 or 24.70 per cent, and someone bullied him or her in class 13 or 7.83 per cent that made them tardy during classes.

• *Internal Factors*

Mainly, as to this factor, the parents value their education as their only treasure for them to inherit 104 or 62.65 per cent, and time management was for the old and mature person with 66 or 39.76 per cent. In addition, respondents had learned from the subject for almost ten

months just to do complacent things 71 or 42.77 per cent. Moreover, they described their teacher as good in his or her field of expertise with 55 or 33.13 per cent, but it was pretty dull how they managed the class encounter 52 or 31.33 per cent. Thus, it could also be summarily stated that grade twelve students were chronically tardy due to the fact that most of them responded that they had worked on other assignments with 100 or 60.24 per cent and most of all, they went to bed at precisely 10:00 PM with 87 or 52.41 per cent.

➤ *A Significant Relationship between the External and Internal Factors of the Respondents when they are Classified as to Gender, Track Enrolled and Combined Monthly Family Income*

As a whole, the computed t-test of gender and track enrolled at 166df at a 0.05 level of significance was lesser than the critical value of 1.960, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis, as could be gleaned in Table 10.

As to combined monthly family income, it mainly resulted in a greater than 0.05 level of significance that made the null hypothesis accepted, for it was not significant except P 5, 000.00 – P 9, 999.00 and P 15, 000.00 – P 19, 999.00 for it showed a p-value of 0.032 and 0.016 respectively that denoted a very low correlation and therefore null hypothesis was rejected.

The data implied, therefore, that there is no significant relationship between age, gender, track enrolled and mostly from other combined monthly family income except P 5, 000.00 – P 9, 999.00 and P 15, 000.00 – P 19, 999.00 and the external and internal factors affecting grade twelve students' tardiness in the Senior High School Department of Kawit National High School; Kawit, Medellin, Cebu for the School Year 2017- 2018.

As could be summarily stated, the computed t-test of External and Internal factors at 166df was lesser than 0.05 level of significance with a critical value of 1.960, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis, as could be gleaned from Table 9.

As to their significant relationship, it mainly resulted in a greater than 0.05 level of significance that made the null hypothesis accepted, for it was not significant.

C. *Conclusion*

Based on the Study's findings, there was no significant relationship between gender, track enrolled, combined monthly family income and the factors affecting grade twelve students' tardiness, for it was lesser than the critical value of 1.960 at a 166df leading to the acceptance of a null hypothesis. It could be concluded, therefore, that the grade twelve students are often late in attending classes for some reasons, namely: distance of home from school, mode of transportation, time to transfer from one room to another, time of travel, time management, personal reasons why late in attending classes, personal view about their teachers and on their degree of learning and their time in going to bed to sleep. On the said findings and the conclusion of the Study, it was hereby recommended that the students need more

motivation and must strictly follow the intervention program to attain zero per cent tardiness rates and to produce quality graduates.

D. Recommendations

Based on the Study's findings, the following summary of the proposed intervention program should be strictly followed and implemented in Kawit National High School, Kawit, Medellin, Cebu, every school year to eliminate students' tardiness of the Grade Twelve students:

First, teachers' knowledge and capabilities should be updated by letting them attend relevant seminars and training workshops, especially in addressing drop-out rates, absenteeism or truancy of students and most of all, students' tardiness.

Second, it could also be enlightening that there should be LAC Session per month so as to know the issues and concerns faced by the teachers in their teaching encounters.

Third, teachers should make the students use their leisure time to do some useful or productive work to prepare them for the future so as to keep away from external and internal factors affecting tardiness and also give them recognition if they don't have late or absences for doing some diligent works every quarter.

Last but not least, home visits must be given priority, for they give proper mentoring and coaching to the teacher and the parent of the chronically tardy students.

➤ *Proposed Interventions in Addressing Grade Twelve Students' Tardiness*

• *Rationale*

Basically, findings showed that the usual factors affecting students' tardiness were: distance from home to school, distance travelled from home to school, time duration transferring from one classroom to another, less number of "chappy" or mini tricycles in the barangay, went to bed to sleep at 10:00 PM for they usually spend most of their time through chatting, texting and surfing the net, working with other assignments, they don't like Mathematics subject as their first subject and most of all they don't value time management. The Senior High School teachers and the grade twelve students, however, could further give some improvements on the teaching competence and on the performance, respectively, as very satisfactory to eliminate students' tardiness.

In lieu, therefore, of the indicated facts of the Study, as previously presented, there was really a need to propose some interventions to improve the teacher-student

relationship, subject-student relationship, teaching competence and performance to eradicate tardiness in the institution. Hence, the hereunder presentation of the intervention program was envisioned to help teachers and students to hone themselves to be the best of their abilities and capabilities.

Herein is a proposed intervention program that aims to enhance students' attendance upon going to school every day and upon entering classes in the morning and in the afternoon session. As such, the program also aimed to enhance the management of parents and classroom management of teachers toward their students whose attendance was both affected externally and internally.

• *General Objectives*

- ✓ *Provide a blueprint for the secondary school administrators and district supervisors on a strategic plan as to how to improve teacher-student relationships, subject-student relationships and parent-student relationships.*
- ✓ *Evaluate the training programs of the teachers on how to handle students effectively and efficiently.*
- ✓ *Motivate the teachers to strive for the best to eliminate students' tardiness and minimize drop-out rates.*
- ✓ *Provide opportunities for the students to transform their selves into a responsible ones in the field of education.*
- ✓ *Develop the student's skills in advanced situations and occupational operations.*
- ✓ *Develop mentoring and coaching toward teachers and parents of chronically tardy students.*

• *Specific Objectives*

- ✓ *Analyze and strategically plan for some training programs so as to meet the zero per cent tardiness of the students in the class.*
- ✓ *Evaluating teachers' performance in managing students by using Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS).*
- ✓ *Follow the mandatory Learning Action Cell (LAC) Session strictly to address issues and concerns met in every teaching encounter.*
- ✓ *Propose weekly monitoring of attendance and weekly counselling for students who were chronically absent within a week.*
- ✓ *Make the students use their leisure time to do some useful or productive work to prepare and equip them in the future so as to keep away from external and internal factors affecting tardiness.*
- ✓ *Implement strictly the home visits of teachers to refrain from students' tardiness and to have a zero drop-out rate.*

The Proposed Interventions Toward The Improvement of Students' Tardiness

Table 10

The Proposed Intervention Enhancement Program

Scheme of Implementation

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies	Persons Involved	Budget	Sources of Budget	Time Frame	Indicators Of Accomplishment	Expected Outcomes	Remarks
Lack of the needed skills and trainings among the Senior High School Teachers in handling chronically tardy students.	Equip the teachers with the needed trainings to eliminate students' tardiness.	Implement seminars, workshops and trainings that address students' tardiness in school. Identify agencies and resource persons to be involved in the trainings. Monitor the	District Supervisor, School Principal/ Administrators, Master Teachers LAC Session Coordinator Advisers/Subje	P 100,000.00	DEPE Fund	May-Mar. May-Mar. Jun.-Mar.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certificates - Narrative Report - Pictures - Liquidation 	The teachers are equipped with knowledge and skills in handling students' tardiness in the Senior High School Department. -0% Tardiness -0% Drop-out rate	

			students' tardiness with the use of Form 2.	ct Teachers		(Daily)		
Lack of Teachers Monitoring	Establish a quarterly evaluation of teachers' performance focusing on to drop-out rates, tardiness and absenteeism.	School Principal Senior High Teachers	Monitor and Evaluate quarterly teachers' performance using Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS)	P 10,000.00	School MOOE	Aug., Oct., and Mar.	- Teachers' RPMS	-0% Tardy - 0% Absences -0% Drop out rate
Lack of teachers' recognition among students with 0% tardiness and absences rate per quarter.	Establish a hundred percent attendance in class and 0% tardiness rates.	School Principal Teachers/Advisers Parents	Check attendance everyday with the use of School Form 2.	P 10,000.00	- School MOOE	June -Mar.	- School Form 2 - Certificates - Pictures	0% Tardiness rates 0% Absences rates
On and Off LAC Session for Teachers	Establish a ten months LAC Session per school year.	School Principal Teachers	Implement LAC Session every 3 rd Friday of the month.	P 35,000	- School MOOE	Jun.- Mar.	- Certificates - Narrative Report	No more issues and concerns faced by teachers in day to day

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